

Sustainable
Medicines
Partnership

Sustainable Medicines Partnership

Sustainable Blister Packaging Eco-design
Research Report

April 2025

Introduction

THE PURPOSE OF THIS WORK

Blister packs are a major packaging format used by the pharmaceuticals and consumer health sector, particularly in Europe. At present, they are not widely recycled due to challenges around packaging design and waste management.

Sustainable packaging was identified as one of the Pillars of Sustainable Medicine, as outlined in the Sustainable Medicines Partnership (SMP) eBook: [Sustainable Medicines eBook](#). Subsequently, the specific issue of Blister Packs was highlighted in the SMP Roundtable Report (2022): [Reducing Single-Use Plastics in Medicine Packaging](#).

Following an incubator session held in April 2023 Blister Pack eco-design was identified as a priority area for further exploration. The topic and proposed guidance was further refined through a workshop hosted by SMP, incorporating input from SMP collaborators and other experts.

This research seeks to gain greater insight into these challenges and identify potential solutions for improving sustainability. The primary focus is on how eco-design principles can be applied to improve blister packaging sustainability, and where wider transformation is required in the recycling ecosystem to improve recycling rates.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- 1) Develop an **understanding of existing standards and guidelines** for relevant packaging materials and identify how these can be leveraged **to shape the SMP's eco-design principles**.
- 2) Determine how **barriers to packaging sustainability can be overcome** based-on **material choice**, use of **additives/composites** and **EoL management**.
- 3) **Gain industry buy-in** by engaging a diverse range of **stakeholders and subject matter experts (SMEs)**, capturing best practice from the Life Sciences sector and beyond, and taking a **solutions-oriented approach** to the core challenges faced.

WHAT WE DID

GUIDELINES AND STANDARDS RESEARCH

Reviewed material standards and guidelines on recyclable plastic packaging to determine industry best practice for sustainable blister packaging.

REGULATORY SCAN

Assessed a selection of regulations in the EU, UK and US to understand key requirements governing material selection during design, and restrictions on waste management at EoL.

GAP ANALYSIS

Conducted a gap analysis to identify the sustainability challenges of blister pack design and how these could be addressed through eco-design and enhanced EoL management systems.

SME INSIGHTS

Conducted interviews with specialists across a blister pack's lifecycle, including upstream design, downstream waste management, and the wider ecosystem.

END-OF-LIFE SYSTEMS MAP

Developed a current state and future-focused EoL systems map to show how non-recyclable blister pack waste is currently managed vs. how recyclable blister packs could be managed in the future.

SYNTHESISE FINDINGS INTO A REPORT

Consolidated all research findings into this report, setting out the steps that industry should take to transition towards sustainable blister packaging, and where challenges remain.

ABOUT THIS DOCUMENT

This document provides an analysis of the current pharmaceutical blister packaging landscape and the opportunities available to improve packaging eco-design. The insights surfaced in this document were gathered through a variety of stakeholder workshops, expert interviews from across the value chain, and desk-based research into packaging standards and regulations.

How to use this document

Section 1 - Gap analysis: Provides an overview of the current state challenges of pharmaceutical blister packaging, the gaps & barriers which hinder the shift towards greater circularity, and how industry can start to take action. The gap analysis is broken down per lifecycle stage: design, collection, and sorting & recycling.

Section 2 - Standards and guidelines: Summarises the key design considerations identified during a scan of packaging standards and guidelines.

Section 3 - Regulatory implications: Outlines several core regulatory requirements which industry must account for during blister packaging design and EoL management.

Section 4 - Recommendations: Sets out some of the key priorities for driving transition towards sustainable blister packs.

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Executive summary

Current blister packaging designs are inherently unsustainable

The way blister packaging is developed leads to challenges across the entire value chain; eco-design principles can solve for some of these challenges.

Challenges across the value chain

Key: Sphere of control during design Broader ecosystem

*Sorting: UK Government's Recyclability assessment methodology for rigid plastics provides limits for use of inks containing carbon black.
 Recycling: Non-washable inks can contaminate recyclate, causing discolouration and reducing quality

There are six key areas that the eco-design principles could address

The eco-design categories are intended to maximise the likelihood of blister recycling at EoL.

Blister pack design is regulated to ensure safety and efficacy

While eco-design can improve blister packaging sustainability, there are some regulatory obligations which set the parameters of what is possible.

PRIMARY PHARMA PACKAGING MUST COMPLY WITH STRICT HYGIENE AND SAFETY STANDARDS

Under the European Pharmacopeia, plastic container manufacturing must be consistently reproducible and preclude any contamination from any other plastics materials.

The FDA states that PCR plastics should not be used in the manufacture of primary packaging.

US regulations directly prohibit the use of PCR plastics in blister pack designs, while UK & EU regulations set material standards which can only be met consistently through virgin plastics use.

The MHRA and EU Pharmacopoeia prohibit the use of 'waste' materials in primary pharmaceutical packaging.

Jurisdiction: UK, EU, US

Source: *Guidance for Industry: Container Closure Systems for Packaging Human Drugs and Biologics (May 1999)*

European Pharmacopoeia 6.0: 3.2.2. Plastic Containers and Closures for Pharmaceutical Use
MHRA interview

TAMPER-EVIDENT PACKAGING

Regulation means that blister packs are inherently single-use in design, given that once the lidding film has been broken the blister pack cannot be reused.

Regulation mandates that manufacturers and packers of over-the-counter (OTC) drugs (with some exceptions) must use a tamper-evident packaging format.

Jurisdiction: US

Source: *PART 211– Current good manufacturing practice for finished pharmaceuticals*

CHILD ACCESS PREVENTION

Any mono-material alternative to aluminium lidding film must comply with child resistant requirements.

The PPPA requires special (child-resistant and senior-friendly) packaging of a wide range of hazardous household products including most oral prescription drugs. Packaging must have a child-resistant effectiveness of at least 85% and senior-friendly effectiveness of at least 90%.

Jurisdiction: US

Source: *Poison Prevention Packaging Act (PPPA)*

EOL TREATMENT AS HAZARDOUS OR NON-HAZARDOUS WASTE

There is divergence in the treatment of packaging waste which previously contained hazardous substances.

UK & EU: Where there is a risk that packaging has hazardous contaminants or residues, it must be treated as hazardous waste. However, if packaging is free from contaminants, it can be treated as packaging waste.

US: Packaging is considered empty and residues are not regulated as hazardous waste providing pharmaceuticals have been removed from the package.

Jurisdiction: UK, EU, US

Source: *Waste Classification: Technical Guidance (WM3);*

Commission notice on technical guidance on the classification of waste (2018/C 124/01)
Resource Conservation and Recovery Act

Eco-design principles for blister packs are just one way to improve sustainability

To ensure sustainable EoL treatment of waste blister packs, systemic transformation is required across the value chain.

1

Closing the loop requires reclassifying chemically recycled plastics

Re-classification of chemically recycled outputs (e.g., naphtha, ethylene) as feedstocks for resin manufacturers and the chemical industry could enable their use as PPP, including in blister packs.

4

Collaboration with the waste value chain

Engage holistically with Producer Responsibility Organisations (PROs) and MRFs and to model how a technically recyclable blister pack could be treated in the waste value chain*.

*This service is offered by some PROs, including Fost Plus in Belgium, to test how a new packaging product would be managed in a MRF.

2

Waste collection and takeback schemes

Establish and scale channels for the collection of waste blister packs, ensuring that any recyclable material can be economically recycled - including through kerbside collection.

5

Engagement with other waste-producing sectors

Facilitate cross-sector dialogue, such as with the Fast -Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) sector, to understand how waste blister packs could align to other waste streams, improving potential for recovery.

3

Role of hospitals and healthcare facilities

As centres with a high concentration of waste blister packs, healthcare facilities could assess how modified waste disposal policies would enable greater blister pack recycling, without over-burdening healthcare professionals.

Key takeaways for the transition towards sustainable blister packaging

The research undertaken has identified these key areas which must be accounted for as part of blister eco-design.

Mono-material blister packs are a key building block, but not the whole answer

The shift towards recyclable mono-material blister packs is part of the long-term solution for improving sustainability and, where feasible, steps should be taken to transition to them. However, these low-barrier solutions are not suitable for all medicines, and their technical recyclability does not mean they are universally recycled in current infrastructure.

Contamination from hazardous substances inhibits recycling

Blister packs which are contaminated by cytotoxic and cytostatic medicines must be treated as hazardous waste at EoL and therefore managed separately to other blister pack waste. A scenario where blister packs containing these types of medicines are visibly different/made of distinct materials would help with the EoL handling.

Consumer behaviour creates a barrier to blister pack collection

There is poor consumer awareness that unused or expired medicines should be returned to pharmacies, not disposed of in general waste (usually the case), or kerbside bins. This rate of general disposal deters waste handlers from recycling blister packs as they are seen as a high-risk contaminant. Greater consumer awareness is a prerequisite for improved collection rates – consumer education is required to i) return unused or partially used medicines to pharmacies; or ii) dispose of empty packs via takeback schemes or kerbside recycling (if scaled in the future).

Market dynamics do not incentivise blister pack recycling

Blister packs, including recyclable mono-material designs, are a relatively low-value, low-volume waste stream, meaning they are not targeted for recycling by waste handlers. Regulation could be used to help incentivise or mandate future recycling, improving material recovery rates. Meanwhile, aligning MRFs blister pack handling procedures with waste streams of a similar risk rating is an area for further investigation.

Regulations prohibit PCR plastics in the US, while safety requirements makes them unviable in Europe

In the US, FDA regulation explicitly states that PCR plastics cannot be used in primary pharmaceutical packaging. However, rules in Europe mean that while PCR plastics with batch level assurances on provenance, purity and contaminants can be used, though this poses technical challenges for mechanical recycling routes.

Replacing non-recyclable and over-engineered blister packs is a significant challenge

Replacing PVC blister packs with mono-material alternatives entails widescale updates to drug Marketing Authorisations; a sizeable undertaking for manufacturers. In addition, low-sensitivity drugs marketed in over-engineered blisters must undergo stability trials to demonstrate viability of alternative packaging, making blister pack replacement a challenging process.

Gap analysis

Conducting the gap analysis

The gap analysis is the key first step in identifying how blister packaging value chains could be adapted to improve sustainability. This section outlines the core findings.

THE PROCESS

9 stakeholders were interviewed from **across the blister packaging lifecycle** (2 **upstream**, 2 **downstream**, and 5 from the **wider ecosystem**) to understand:

- The **current state** of blister packaging sustainability;
- The **gaps / barriers** to improving blister pack sustainability;
- The **opportunities** available to drive the transition towards sustainable solutions; and
- Other key **opportunity enablers and insights** across the various stages of the blister pack lifecycle.

The findings from this research were grouped into six provisional **categories for eco-design principles**:

1. Number of materials	4. Ink usage
2. Type of materials	5. Colours and dyes
3. Barrier layer and coatings	6. Weight, size and perforation

In addition, a **7th category - consumer behaviour** - was identified as a key improvement area to maximise the potential impact of these principles.

A validation workshop conducted with SMP members and other industry experts was used to prioritise opportunities and identify the key actions for achieving these.

THE OUTPUT

To synthesise insights from the gap analysis, this section outlines key challenges and opportunities for improving blister pack sustainability across three distinct stages of the value chain:

- i. Design**
- ii. Collection**
- iii. Sorting and recycling**

For each of these stages, the following method was applied:

CURRENT STATE

Assesses the current landscape of blister pack designs, waste collection and EoL sorting/recycling.

GAPS AND BARRIERS

Outlines the sustainability challenges of this landscape and why they are difficult to overcome.

OPPORTUNITIES FOR SUSTAINABILITY

Proposes a series of actions which industry could explore to improve the sustainability of blister packs at each stage.

Most blister packs are not currently designed for recyclability, but there are a range of opportunities to address this (1/2)

Our research found that while blister pack sustainability can be improved through material choice, not all limitations can be addressed.

Most blister packs are not currently designed for recyclability, but there are a range of opportunities to address this (2/2)

Beyond material choice, there are several other ways that blister pack sustainability can be improved.

	CURRENT STATE OF BLISTER DESIGN	GAPS AND BARRIERS	OPPORTUNITIES FOR SUSTAINABILITY
Barrier layer and coatings	<p>PVDC is often selected as a barrier coating: PVDC is coated on some PVC to provide additional oxygen and moisture protection. However, it has the same harmful impacts as PVC at EoL.</p>	<p>PVDC is effective and hard to replace: PVDC provides a cheap, effective barrier for many drugs, maintaining drug efficacy while complying with safety standards.</p>	<p>Applying recyclable barriers and coatings: Industry should research how the application of recyclable barriers can be made compatible with blister thermoforming at commercial scale, including sandwiching innovative coatings between mono-material layers.</p>
Ink usage	<p>Printing on lidding film: Brand and medical information must be printed on the blister pack lidding film to provide necessary product and safety information to consumers.</p>	<p>Excessive ink use can impede blister pack sorting: If applied in excessive quantities, ink can alter material reflectivity, potentially inhibiting the Near-Infrared (NIR) sorting process as recyclable mono-material blisters are scaled in the future.</p> <p>Ink reduces recycle quality: Non-washable inks can contaminate recycle, causing discolouration and reducing quality.</p>	<p>Minimise blister pack printing: Where viable, minimise printing on recyclable mono-material blister packs to improve sortability and recycling rates.</p> <p>Select water-soluble inks: All information printed on blister packs could use water-soluble inks, reducing contamination risk associated with some inks and maintaining recycle quality.</p>
Weight, size and perforation	<p>Small format packaging: Blisters are a type of lightweight, small format packaging which are not sought for recycling at EoL.</p> <p>Perforations: Some blister packs have perforations to allow single units to be removed from the pack.</p>	<p>Poor compatibility with sorting infrastructure: Blister designs which are smaller than 25cm² will often be directed to the residual waste stream, including those which are technically recyclable mono-materials.</p>	<p>Design for compatibility with waste infrastructure: Explore methods for increasing compatibility of blister pack designs with EoL processing. For example, creating single, elongated blister packs which are folded into boxes, rather than two separate packs.</p> <p>Phase out perforated designs: Reduce excess waste produced through the tearing of perforated blisters.</p>

Opportunity enablers and insights

Leverage advancements in the food sector

The pharmaceuticals industry should leverage insights from the food sector on how to adopt and apply recyclable barriers and coatings at scale. **Note:** technical challenges with the thermoforming process means that not all learnings will be transferable to blisters.

Prioritise OTC and new drugs

Proof of concepts for sustainable blister packs should focus on mass market OTC drugs and new drugs being developed to maximise solution impact and minimise marketing authorisation updates.

Identifying the appropriate collection method is key to improving EoL management

The two main options available for blister pack collection are takeback schemes and kerbside recycling. However, both face challenges.

	CURRENT STATE OF WASTE BLISTER COLLECTION	GAPS AND BARRIERS	OPPORTUNITIES FOR SUSTAINABILITY	<u>Opportunity enablers and insights</u>
Consumer behaviour	<p>Takeback schemes: Blister pack takeback schemes, such as that operated by Boots in the UK, have recently been established to incentivise consumers to return waste blister packs at EoL.</p> <p>Kerbside collection: Kerbside collection is not currently available for recycling blister packs, meaning blister packs are disposed of in the general mixed waste stream.</p>	<p>Commercial challenges of takeback schemes: Takeback schemes place the burden on consumers to return blister packs to stores and come at significant cost to operators, potentially inhibiting scalability.</p> <p>Contamination risk in kerbside collection: There is resistance from waste handlers to separately collect blister packs due to the risk of filled blisters being incorrectly disposed of and contaminating other material streams.</p>	<p>Optimise disposal and collection in healthcare facilities: As centres with high volumes of blister packaging, healthcare facilities could explore options available to collect waste blisters for recycling.</p> <p>Consumer information: Improving consumer awareness that unused blisters must be returned to pharmacies could reduce contamination risk and support the future kerbside collection of mono-material blisters.</p>	<p>Analyse data on where drugs are consumed</p> <p>Identify the areas in which drugs are most frequently consumed to target blister collection systems.</p>
Number of materials	<p>Blister packs do not align to a single waste stream: Multi-material blister packs cannot be disposed of in a single recycling stream as the adhesive prevents material separation.</p>	<p>Multi-materials and PVC are not targeted by recyclers: These materials are costly to recycle and have less value than other packaging types, meaning they are not separately collected for recycling by municipalities.</p>	<p>Alignment of materials to household waste streams: Mono-material blisters made from materials already accepted in kerbside collection systems are likely to achieve higher recovery rates than those which are not.</p>	<p>Collaboration amongst healthcare facilities</p> <p>Blister disposal systems must be simple and intuitive to support healthcare professionals, so sharing best practice is essential.</p>
Type of materials	<p>PVC packaging is not collected for recycling: Unlike other polymers - such as PET, PP and PE - PVC is not separately collected for recycling in municipal waste.</p>	<p>Note: Commercial recycling exists for some PVC products, including piping, but there is currently no cost-effective method to collect PVC blisters for this recycling stream.</p>	<p>Engage PVC recyclers: Takeback schemes collecting PVC blisters could explore how large batches could be transferred to PVC recycling facilities for higher-grade recycling.</p>	
Weight, size and perforation	<p>Perforated blisters are disposed of in general waste: Fragments of perforated blister pack waste are discarded in general waste but are also more likely to result in litter than non-perforated blister packs.</p>	<p>Perforated blister packs are too small for separate collection: Once torn from the main pack, waste from perforated blister packs cannot be separately collected for recycling, even if made from recyclable mono-material.</p>	<p>Education and consumer information: Where blister packs are not modified to design-out perforations, consumers should be educated on how perforated blisters can impact EoL disposal, including through packaging information.</p>	<p>Self-return envelope</p> <p>Pharmaceuticals manufacturers could trial self-return envelopes for recovering blister pack waste. Similar trials have been conducted for collecting injector pens.</p>

The sorting and recycling of blister packaging is constrained by current designs, but mono-material blisters still face challenges (1/2)

Blister designs are generally not compatible with sorting and recycling infrastructure, but there are opportunities to change this.

CURRENT STATE OF WASTE BLISTER TREATMENT

GAPS AND BARRIERS

OPPORTUNITIES FOR SUSTAINABILITY

Number of materials

Multi-material blister pack recycling is not currently available at scale: Certain companies are capable of recycling blister packs, such as MYGroup in the UK, but these facilities are not widespread, and the output is often a downcycled mix of polyolefins.

Regulation does not incentivise recycling for multi-material packaging: Current regulatory frameworks do not mandate or incentivise the recycling of multi-material medical packaging.

Sorting multi-material blisters is an inconsistent process: If placed in a recycling stream and not directed to residual waste (see next slide), multi-material blisters will be sorted based on the side of the pack facing up when scanned by NIR, not material weight.

Market forces are insufficient to increase recycling: Without incentives, waste sorters and recyclers will only target high-value waste streams for recycling. Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) helps to cover higher costs for hard-to-recycle materials, but medical packaging is often exempt.

Inconsistent sorting of blister packs contaminates recycling streams: Multi-material blister pack waste contaminates whichever recycling stream it is sorted into, reducing the quality of the recycle.

Align with other waste streams: Mono-material blister recycling may be limited if packs do not align to other waste streams.

Regulatory reform to improve eco-design and recycling: Hard-to-recycle blisters could be disincentivised and proceeds used to fund their more costly processing, including through chemical recycling. This could help drive the uptake of recyclable mono-material blisters.

Explore potential for wide-scale Alu-Alu blister recycling: Belgium currently recycles >50% aluminium Alu-Alu blisters using eddy current separators (ECS) and special filtration infrastructure to remove hydrogen chloride gas from PVC layers. This could serve as a blueprint for other countries.

Non-food contact waste streams: Aligning blister waste to HDPE household goods packaging, such as detergent, could increase recycling while minimising contamination risk.

Type of materials

PVC blisters can be difficult to sort: PVC has a similar density to PET, reducing the effectiveness of some sorting methods, including float-sink separation.

Functionally zero recycling of PVC blisters: PVC packaging is not recycled by most Material Recovery Facilities (MRFs) as a potential contaminant of other waste streams.

Limited incentive to scale PVC recycling: The contamination risks associated with PVC means that replacing it is often seen as a more sustainable solution than recycling it.

Industry resistance: Investment made in PVC blister pack machinery means that some companies may resist the transition towards recyclable mono-material blisters.

Assess how chemical recycling could be applied: While still an emerging technology, chemical recycling could be used to increase circularity of hard-to-replace PVC blisters where packaging re-design is not viable.

Note: This would rely on optimised collection and sorting systems, as chemical recycling typically requires 20-24 tonnes of the same material for a single cycle.

Opportunity enablers and insights

Leverage new AI capabilities

Explore how new AI capabilities being employed by MRFs can be used to more effectively identify and sort blister pack waste.

Greater collaboration with MRFs

Undertake MRF testing when adopting recyclable blister packs to understand how they are sorted to improve recovery rates.

Alignment with new packaging rules

Consult MRFs on how the UK's 2027 municipal waste requirements for flexible PP and PE recycling could support PP / PE blister recycling.

The sorting and recycling of blister packaging is constrained by current designs, but mono-material blisters still face challenges (2/2)

Blister designs are not compatible with sorting and recycling infrastructure, but there are opportunities to change this going forward.

CURRENT STATE OF WASTE BLISTER TREATMENT

GAPS AND BARRIERS

OPPORTUNITIES FOR SUSTAINABILITY

Barrier layer and coatings

Functionally zero recycling of PVDC-coated blisters: As for PVC blisters, PVDC-coated blisters are not sought for recycling by MRFs due to their impact as a potential contaminant of other waste streams.

PVDC is difficult to identify during sorting: MRFs do not have the technology to identify and remove packaging which contains PVDC as a barrier layer.

Limited incentive to scale PVDC recycling: While new methods have been developed for PVDC sorting and recycling*, these have not been implemented at scale and still require more processing than alternative coatings.

Recyclable barrier and coatings:

Developing a commercial scale process in which recyclable barrier coatings can be applied between blister pack layers will enable enhanced barrier performance while maintaining recyclability.

Note: Barriers should not exceed 5% of packaging weight to ensure high recyclability performance.

Colours and dyes

Mono-material blister packs are hard to distinguish from food-contact materials: Mono-material blister packs are often transparent PP or PE, making them difficult to distinguish from transparent food-contact packaging of the same material. However, the use of colours or dyes would reduce recyclability and impact solution circularity.

Food-contact recycling streams must not be contaminated: Mono-material blister packs present a potential contamination risk for MRFs, who must maintain high safety standards for recycle to be used in food-contact packaging. As such recyclable blister packs should be distinguishable from food-contact packaging to allow them to be recycled in a different stream.

Apply markers to enable blister identification:

To avoid using harmful colours or dyes for identification, the use of invisible markers, including chemical markers, could help MRFs separate blister pack waste from food-contact streams; reducing contaminants and maintaining recyclability.

Weight, size and perforation

Blister packs are currently sorted into the residual waste stream: If placed in the recycling stream, blister packs will often be removed by sieving drums before they reach NIR sorting due to their small size.

Small format packaging is often a similar size to the debris MRFs look to remove: The sieving drum is a necessary step to remove debris, such as broken glass and shredded paper, from waste streams before materials are separated for recycling. Often, blisters smaller than 25cm² will be removed by the sieving drum and treated as debris.

Design for practical recycling, not technical recyclability: New blister pack designs must become more compatible with MRF sorting infrastructure to be recycled at EoL. This means considering pack shape and size, not just material recyclability. Elongated, foldable blister packs represent a potential solution for this without increasing raw materials usage.

Opportunity enablers and insights

Tracer-Based Sorting (TBS)

Emerging TBS technology allows fractions from the same waste stream to be accurately and efficiently separated using fluorescent tracers. This would enable blister pack PP/PE to be kept separate from food-contact PP/PE. **Note:** TBS is an emerging technology and barriers to adoption still remain.

Treatment of hazardous substances

Blister packs which are contaminated by cytotoxic and cytostatic drugs must be disposed of in the hazardous waste stream (see page 23). Resultantly, blister pack recyclability is not a priority for these drugs.

Standards and guidelines findings

There are clear standards and guidelines on how packaging materials and structures impact sortability and recyclability

Key themes identified in our Standards and Guidelines review are highlighted below. Sources reviewed are documented in Appendix A.

	Key theme	Standards/ Guidelines	Standard-specific guidance
	<p>Packaging should have a mono-material design and avoid multi-material laminates, improving sortability and recyclability</p>	<p>CiAI GDR APR CEFLEX WRAP APCO</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consorzio imballaggi alluminio (CiAI): Single-material packaging is easier to identify in waste sorting, while multilayer laminates make it difficult, if not impossible, to separate materials for recycling. • Golden Design Rules (GDR): Multi-material designs contaminate the recycling stream, resulting in lower quality recycle. For example, PET recycled with PE contamination becomes cloudy and yellow. • Association of Plastic Recyclers (APR): Metal components can cause NIR sorters in MRFs to misidentify a polymer-based container as metal, and therefore incorrectly direct it to a metal stream. • Circular Economy for Flexible Packaging (CEFLEX): For flexible plastics, non-polymer layers, including paper and aluminium, are not compatible with recycling. • Waste and Resources Action Programme (WRAP): Mono lidding film should be the same material as the packaging tray when permanently attached for recycling via kerbside collection. • Australian Packaging Covenant Organisation (APCO): Use only one polymer for all packaging components.
	<p>PVC and PVDC are disruptive materials which are highly incompatible with the recycling process</p>	<p>GDR WRAP APR APCO CPRRA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDR: Small concentrations of PVC (0.005% by weight) leads to quality reductions in recycled PET as recyclers are not equipped with machinery to remove these quantities. In addition, acid formation during breakdown is corrosive to metal equipment, and therefore would be disruptive to pyrolysis-based chemical recycling. • WRAP: Any pack containing PVC components is considered non-recyclable. Similarly, any PVDC used as a barrier layer will prevent a packaging from being recyclable. • APR: PVC degrades to hydrochloric acid and chlorine, so even a small amount of PVC being processed with other polymers renders them useless. The PVC waste stream is also too small to consider recycling separately. • APCO: PVC should be avoided as it is a similar density to PET so is difficult to separate in the recycling process using float-sink separation. • China Plastics Reuse and Recycling Association (CPRRA): PVDC, and other degradable additives which make packaging sink, are not recyclable.

Beyond packaging materials and structures, standards and guidelines detail how barrier layers and additives impact recyclability

Key themes identified in our Standards and Guidelines review are highlighted below. Sources reviewed are documented in Appendix A.

	Key theme	Standards/ Guidelines	Standard-specific guidance
	<p>Barrier layers can be compatible with recycling processes, but this can vary by geography and material</p>	<p>WRAP GDR APR CEFLEX APCO CPRRA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WRAP: A EVOH barrier layer less than 5% of the packaging weight is acceptable for recycling. Lightly metallised films are not currently widely recycled in the UK and more widely recycled in EU. They are considered compatible with PE or PP mechanical recycling. • GDR: Barriers which have been proven not to limit packaging recyclability are preferred- AlOx, SiOx, EVOH and PVOH are recommended examples. • APR: EVOH is not separable in the recycling process and therefore will become part of the recycled polymer. However, Maleated polyethylene (PE-g-MAH) tie layers can be used with EVOH to improve its adhesion to HDPE or PP and have been shown to improve compatibility during the recycling process. • CEFLEX: Maximum 5% of total packaging weight can comprise barriers, adhesives and coatings before recyclability is impacted (material type permitting). • APCO: EVOH is compatible at lower levels with PP and HDPE recycling (where barrier is kept to a minimal) but can cause significant issues in PET recycling. • CPRRA: SiOx plasma coating is compatible with PET recycling process.
	<p>Additives can impact both the sorting and recycling process</p>	<p>RECYCLASS APR APCO</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RECYCLASS: Use of water-soluble adhesives enhances recyclability. • APR: High-density additives can cause PP or PE to sink in the float-sink tank, potentially sending them to the wrong waste stream. • APR: Optical brighteners can also be detrimental to plastics recycling but are hard to detect until late in the recycling process. • APCO: Optical brighteners can cause unacceptable fluorescence in the next product/packaging made from recycled HDPE. • APCO: Avoid using mineral fillers that alter the polymer density and contaminate the finished recycled material.

Packaging colour and size primarily impact material sortability, while recycled content helps to drive circular packaging systems

Key themes identified in our Standards and Guidelines review are highlighted below. Sources reviewed are documented in Appendix A.

	Key theme	Standards/ Guidelines	Standard-specific guidance
	<p>Clear packaging design improves potential for high-value recycling</p>	<p>GDR RECYCLASS APR CEFLEX APCO</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDR: Clear and transparent PET is preferred over blue or green PET as they provide the greatest opportunity for the packaging to be recycled back into new high-value products. • RECYCLASS: Clear and white HDPE and PP are fully compatible with the recycling process, provided they are sorted into distinct waste streams. By comparison light & dark colours have limited-to-low compatibility. • APR: NIR sorting technology cannot distinguish one dark polymer from another, increasing the risk of poor sorting and contamination. Unpigmented PP and HDPE packaging is preferred, but both are commonly coloured, so volumes and markets exist for coloured material, and it is economical to process. • APR: For PP packaging, the material should have an NIR reflectance of >10%. PP packaging with an NIR reflectance of ≤10% has a high probability of not being recognised correctly by NIR technology and could therefore be sent to the wrong plastics stream. • CEFLEX: Pigments should be clear, natural or paler colours. • APCO: Biggest barrier to HDPE recycling is the use of dark colours, which hinder separation and reprocessing.
	<p>Small-format packaging waste is unlikely to be recycled</p>	<p>WRAP APR</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WRAP: Items smaller than 40mm diameter are considered non-recyclable. • APR: Waste smaller than 25cm² will likely be directed to residue waste stream.
	<p>Maximise the use of recycled content in packaging</p>	<p>APR APCO</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APR: The use of PCR PVC, PP and HDPE in all packages and items is encouraged to the maximum amount technically and economically feasible. • APCO: Incorporate recycled content to help create and support sustainable end markets for recycled polymers.

Regulatory scan findings

Regulations governing pharmaceutical packaging designs limit the viability of circular solutions

Blister pack designs must comply with regulations on material type and accessibility requirements to be marketed.

Regulation	Country / Region	Regulatory consideration	Implications for blister packaging
Guidance for Industry: Container Closure Systems for Packaging Human Drugs and Biologics (May 1999)	US	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PCR plastics prohibited: The manufacturing of primary pharmaceutical packaging should not use PCR plastics under US regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporating PCR plastic content into blister pack designs is prohibited. However, the regulation does not mention post-industrial recycled (PIR) plastics, providing a potential opportunity for circularity.
European Pharmacopoeia 6.0: 3.2.2. Plastic Containers and Closures for Pharmaceutical Use	EU/UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manufacturing must be consistent and preclude contamination: The production of plastic pharmaceutical packaging must ensure reproducibility for subsequent manufacturing and preclude the possibility of contamination from other plastic materials or their ingredients. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While PCR plastic is not explicitly prohibited by the regulation, it is impractical to produce consistent PCR plastic free from other plastic contaminants. However, chemical recycling could enable this in the future.
PART 211– Current good manufacturing practice for finished pharmaceuticals	US	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tamper evident packaging: Each manufacturer and packer who packages an OTC drug product (except a dermatological, dentifrice, insulin, or lozenge product) for retail sale shall package the product in a tamper-evident package, if this product is accessible to the public while held for sale. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The regulation mandates a single-use design, given that once the lidding film has been broken, the blister pack cannot be reused.
Poison Prevention Packaging Act (PPPA)	US	<p>The PPPA requires special (child-resistant and adult-friendly) packaging of a wide range of hazardous household products including most oral prescription drugs. This includes the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reuse: The package cannot be reused. • Children resistant effectiveness: The package must have a child-resistant effectiveness of at least 85% before demonstration, and at least 80% after demonstration. The package must also have a senior-friendly effectiveness of at least 90%. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPPA has the same single-use implications as for Part 211. • Mono-material alternatives to blister pack lidding film must comply with child resistant requirements.

Regulations on EoL treatment of packaging depend on the presence of hazardous medicines and contaminants

Blister packs which contain residues of hazardous contaminants may be recyclable in the US, but not in the UK or EU.

Regulation	Country / Region	Regulatory consideration	Implications for blister packaging
<p>UK - Waste Classification: Technical Guidance (WM3)</p> <p>EU - Commission notice on technical guidance on the classification of waste (2018/C 124/01)</p>	<p>UK/EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contaminated packaging treated as hazardous waste: Packaging containing residues or contaminated by hazardous substances must be treated as hazardous waste. As such, if a medicine contains hazardous substances and there is residual content in the packaging, the packaging must be classified and treated the same as these contents. • Empty and non-contaminated packaging treated as packaging waste: Packaging which held hazardous substances but is now empty (e.g. the contaminants have been removed by effective cleaning) should be treated as packaging waste, not hazardous waste. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where there is a risk that waste blister packaging is contaminated by hazardous substances, it must be treated as hazardous waste, preventing future recyclability. • It is impractical to undertake cleaning of blister packs to ensure they are free of any contaminants or residues, meaning they will typically be disposed of as hazardous waste.
<p>Resource Conservations and Recovery Act</p>	<p>US</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Packaging contaminants not treated as hazardous waste: Where unit-dose containers, such as blister packs, are considered empty of acute and non-acute hazardous waste pharmaceuticals, the residues are not regulated as hazardous waste. As such, it is not necessary to demonstrate the removal of residues, and the packaging can be disposed of as non-hazardous waste. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing that hazardous medicines have been removed from the packaging, waste blister packs can be treated as non-hazardous waste, enabling future recycling.

Recommendations

Overall, several key areas exist which could help to advance blister packaging eco-design

Based on the research undertaken, six areas have emerged as key priorities for driving transition to sustainable blister packs. Best practices from other industries, such as food packaging, can be leveraged within these; existing solutions can be adapted for pharmaceutical use.

1 | Consolidate mono-material blister designs around a single successor to PVC

To help achieve the scale needed to encourage MRFs to target blister pack waste for recycling, industry should consolidate around a mono-material replacement for PVC based blisters. This will help provide a standardised packaging format for MRFs to sort into the appropriate fraction and prevent fragmentation for sustainable blister pack solutions. Aligning blister handling procedures in MRFs with waste of a similar risk rating, is an area for further investigation.

2 | Assess the opportunities for using chemically recycled, contaminant-free PCR plastics in blister pack designs

Blister pack manufacturers should examine how the transition towards chemical recycling could enable the regulatory-compliant use of PCR plastics in blister packs. Providing that suppliers can consistently obtain sources of the same virgin-equivalent, contaminant-free feedstock, in line with European Pharmacopeia standards, recycled content could be a viable solution for driving circularity in the future.

3 | Scale solutions which apply recyclable barrier coatings between mono-material layers

Where blister packs require higher barrier protection, industry should look to scale solutions which apply barrier coatings in-between layers of mono-material polymers. This enables greater moisture and air protection while maintaining the performance of the barrier layer during thermoforming.

4 | Develop regulation to mandate or incentivise eco-design, where appropriate

Regulatory intervention could help to incentivise the adoption of recyclable blister packs. This may include targeted EPR-style contributions which charge more for non-recyclable or hard-to-recycle designs, including PVC and multi-materials. This would encourage the move towards mono-materials, where appropriate, and would help to subsidise EoL costs. **Note:** Maintaining drug safety and efficacy is paramount, and regulatory interventions should be limited to drugs where a safe and viable blister pack alternative exists.

5 | Packaging markers and identification technologies

Sustainable blister designs could leverage new technologies for sorting plastic packaging into different waste fractions, for example through Tracer-Based Sorting. This technology allows packaging of the same polymer to be sorted into its application-specific waste stream, such as medical packaging or food-contact packaging, to maintain recyclate quality for future applications. As MRFs begin to adopt the AI and NIR technologies to sort waste plastics this way, blister pack recycling rates could be improved.

6 | Design blister packs to be identifiable in the appropriate waste stream

Focus on how blister packs can be designed to be recycled with packaged household goods, for example, detergent and shampoo bottles. These packaged goods present a lower contamination risk for recyclers than food-contact packaging, and aligning blisters to a higher-volume waste stream could help to increase material recovery and recycling.

Next steps

This work lays the foundation for defining eco-design principles

The research conducted for this report was informed by the EU Joint Research Centre's (JRC) paper on eco-design for textiles*, but important gaps remain to make decisions on the specific eco-design principles.

Reviewed **material standards and guidelines** from the **packaging industry** to outline **best practice** for blister pack designs.

The JRC includes analysis of legislation and strategies

Conducted **interviews with experts** within the blister pack ecosystem to understand **opportunities, challenges** and **regulatory implications** of the transition to sustainable blisters.

Supported analysis of legislation and strategies, market analysis and user behaviour, per the JRC

Assessed **regulations in EU, UK and US** to understand the current regulatory landscape, including constraints

The JRC includes analysis of legislation and strategies

Developed **current EoL systems map** and an **ideal future state systems map** for **blister packs**, including product / packaging takebacks (EU, UK, USA)

The JRC includes insight into the life-cycle stages; and markets in scope

Conducted a **gap analysis** to determine the **current sustainability challenges** of blister packs, and how **blister designs** and **EoL systems** can be made more sustainable.

The JRC includes insight into the life-cycle stages

FOLLOW ON ACTIONS

Seven follow on actions were identified and are summarised on the next page.

Follow-on actions

- 1 **Engage stakeholders**
Bring blister film manufacturers into discussions and conduct pilot studies to model, refine and implement the eco-design recommendations.
- 2 **Testing and validation**
Work with Material Recovery Facilities (MRF) to test recyclable blister designs and evaluate sorting capabilities.
- 3 **Consumer analysis and education**
Analyse consumer behavior to inform educational campaigns aimed at improving blister pack disposal practices.
- 4 **Regulatory exploration**
Collaborate with regulators to explore incentives for adopting recyclable designs, such as extended producer responsibility schemes.
- 5 **Implementation costs**
Conduct a cost-benefit analysis of the costs of involved in transitioning to recyclable materials, including equipment upgrades and regulatory testing.
- 6 **Global considerations**
Explore regulatory and logistical differences in key markets, including environmental hotspots or areas to ensure global applicability of recommendations.
- 7 **Monitoring and evaluation**
Develop KPIs to track progress, such as recycling rates and reductions in non-recyclable materials, to measure the impact of the recommendations over time.

*<https://susproc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/product-bureau/product-groups/467/home>

Follow-on actions

Potential actions and future work to be pursued to maximise on the progress this work has achieved.

- 1 | Engage stakeholders**
Bring blister film manufacturers into discussions and conduct pilot studies to model, refine and implement the eco-design recommendations.
- 2 | Testing and validation**
Work with Material Recovery Facilities (MRFs) to test recyclable blister designs and evaluate sorting capabilities.
- 3 | Consumer analysis and education**
Analyse consumer behavior to inform educational campaigns aimed at improving blister pack disposal practices.
- 4 | Regulatory exploration**
Collaborate with regulators to explore incentives for adopting recyclable designs, such as extended producer responsibility schemes.
- 5 | Implementation costs**
Conduct scenario modelling of the costs of involved in transitioning to recyclable materials, including equipment upgrades and regulatory testing.
- 6 | Global considerations**
Explore regulatory and logistical differences in key markets, including environmental, like India or China to ensure global applicability of recommendations.
- 7 | Monitoring and evaluation**
Develop KPIs to track progress, such as recycling rates and reductions in non-recyclable materials, to measure the impact of the recommendations over time.

Appendix

Appendix A: Standards and guidelines reviewed

Standards and Guidelines	Source	Key
Packaging material recycling	ISO/TR 17098:2013	ISO
Best practice design for recycling and guide to selecting materials	Australian Packaging Covenant Organisation	APCO
Golden Design Rules (GDR)	Consumer good forum - Waste coalition of action	CGF
Design for Recycling Guidelines	RecyClass	RecyClass
Defining What's Recyclable	WRAP	WRAP
Design Guide for Plastic Recyclability	The Association of Plastic Recyclers	APR
Designing for a Circular Economy for Flexible packaging	A Circular Economy for Flexible Packaging	CEFLEX
Recyclability Design Guide for PET and HDPE Packaging Container	Chinese Plastics Reuse and Recycle Association	CPRRA

Methodology note

The review of standards and guidelines was carried out through desktop analysis from publicly available sources. These were reviewed considering the applicability of materials relevant to blister packaging. Alongside this, packaging regulations from UK, EU and the US were reviewed for their applicability to blister packaging.

Limitations

Our findings within this regulations and standards review are based on findings as of 31/03/2024 and are limited to information that was publicly available up to and on that date.

Appendix B: Current EoL Systems Map

Systems map shows what should happen to a blister pack during its lifecycle based on current waste regulations, although this may not always happen in practice. Systems map assumes waste blisters placed in general waste, not recycling stream.

Appendix C: Future EoL Systems Map (1/2)

Systems map shows what an ideal future state could look like for a blister pack's lifecycle to improve recyclability. The first two stages remain the same as the current systems map, except blister designs are recyclable mono-materials.

Appendix C: Future EoL Systems Map (2/2)

Systems map shows what an ideal future state could look like for a blister pack's lifecycle to improve recyclability. The first two stages remain the same as the current systems map, except blister designs are recyclable mono-materials.

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This work was led through the SMP Packaging Working Group by:

Nazneen Rahman (YewMaker, SMP Director)
Joe Muscat (Haleon)
Duncan Flack (Honeywell)

The SMP is convened by YewMaker, please visit www.yewmaker.com/SMP for more information